

Co-occurrence network analysis of translation: a case study of *Jabberwocky*

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Abstract

This work introduces a new framework for the quantitative and comparative analysis of literary translation phenomena using graph attributes derived from SpeechGraphs software. SpeechGraphs (SG) takes text as input and produces graph features as output. In the context of natural languages and word-level networks, SG belongs to the category of "co-occurrence graphs," which model co-occurrence patterns between successive words. SG was initially developed to help diagnose schizophrenia and bipolar disorder, achieving success through graph analysis. Although numerous mathematical quantification approaches have emerged in recent years, graph analysis has yet to be explored in Translation Studies. Graph attributes are employed to visually and statistically reveal hidden patterns within the word-level co-occurrence language network. This approach is particularly effective for identifying patterns that are difficult to detect without digital enhancements. We chose Lewis Carroll's widely translated nonsense poem, *Jabberwocky*, as the focus of our case study.

Keywords: translation, quantitative analysis, graph network analysis, *Jabberwocky*.

1. Re-configuring the problem

Translation Studies is a field shaped by concepts such as analogy, equivalence, correspondence, and similarity. As Stecconi (2004, p. 478-82) argues, translation necessitates perceiving texts as analogous or similar. Equivalence is a foundational concept in this discipline, with Roman Jakobson defining it as the conveyance of two equivalent messages in two different codes (Jakobson, [1959] 2012, p. 127–28). Equivalence is not limited to the word level, as Meschonnic notes (2011, p. 71). Eugene Nida distinguishes between formal and dynamic equivalence (Nida [1964] 2012, p. 144), while Werner Koller identifies five types of equivalence: denotative, connotative, text-normative, pragmatic, and stylistic (Koller, 1995). Mona Baker argues that equivalence occurs at various levels, including word, collocation and idiom, grammar, text, and pragmatics ([1992] 2011, also Atã and Queiroz, 2016). Katharina Reiss developed a translation-oriented text typology grounded in the classification of three fundamental communicative functions outlined by the psychologist Karl Bühler (1934[2011]) in his *Organon Model*. In her work, Reiss (2000) proposed that equivalence at the level of text type should serve as the primary standard for evaluating translations. According to her framework, the target text must preserve the text type of the source text to achieve functional equivalence. Some scholars prefer the notion of "correspondence," as espoused by Holmes (1998), who views the translator as a decoder and re-encoder of a "hierarchy of correspondences." However, the degree and form of equivalence identified in the source-target relationship can vary depending on multiple parameters. Kalevi Kull (2023, p. 80) defines translation as

a mediated code-based or habit-based transformation of sign(s) which creates a sensible correspondence between source and target pattern. We can use mapping as its synonym. The correspondence usually preserves at least some features of relational structure. The invariant

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features imply an opportunity for evaluation of the translation in terms of quality or adequacy of the mapping, or for the introduction of some measures characterizing the aspects by which the structure (possibly including the context) is conveyed and transferred.

How can rates of invariance in "features of relational structures" be measured between source and target texts in interlinguistic translation? How can we comparatively measure the equivalence between different targets derived from the same source by examining their structures, components, and internal relationships? This paper introduces a framework for the quantitative and comparative analysis of literary translation phenomena using graph attributes derived from word co-occurrence networks generated by SpeechGraphs software. These networks consist of words as nodes, which are linked to other nodes if they appear adjacent to each other in a text. Co-occurrence is a term that can describe various phenomena, as long as there is an interconnection of a specified unit of text based on their paired presence. In our case, we use words as nodes that are positioned side by side (edges).

Although numerous mathematical quantification approaches in Translation Studies have emerged in recent years, graph analysis has yet to be employed to quantitatively model the relation between source and target texts. Translation can, therefore, be described as a relationship between two systems of word co-occurrence. We present a computational framework for the quantitative and comparative analysis of literary translation phenomena using graph analysis with SpeechGraphs software.³ This paper has three primary aims: (i) to introduce a quantitative methodology (SG) that has not yet been applied in the domain of interlinguistic translation studies, (ii) to analyze source and target literary texts using graph attributes, and (iii) to compare different translations of the same source text, also using graph attributes. For our case study, we selected Lewis Carroll's widely translated nonsense poem *Jabberwocky*.

2. *Jabberwocky*

Jabberwocky is a nonsense poem found within the children's book *Through the Looking-Glass, and What Alice Found There*, a continuation of the world-famous *Alice's Adventures in Wonderland*. It was written by Charles Dodgson under the pseudonym Lewis Carroll, who also authored other, less famous children's books and several poems (Cohen, 2015). *Jabberwocky* is not long, especially considering it narrates an epic battle against a creature called the Jabberwock. The poem consists of 28 verses divided into seven stanzas, with the first and seventh stanzas being identical. The poem contains 167 tokens and 92 types.

Source (English):

Jabberwocky

'Twas brillig, and the slithy toves
Did gyre and gimble in the wabe:
All mimsy were the borogoves,
And the mome raths outgrabe.

³ For an introduction and detailed description of the SG, see Mota et al. (2012).

"Beware the Jabberwock, my son!
 The jaws that bite, the claws that catch!
 Beware the Jubjub bird, and shun
 The frumious Bandersnatch!"

He took his vorpal sword in hand:
 Long time the manxome foe he sought --
 So rested he by the Tumtum tree,
 And stood awhile in thought.

And, as in uffish thought he stood,
 The Jabberwock, with eyes of flame,
 Came whiffling through the tulgey wood,
 And burbled as it came!

One, two! One, two! And through and through
 The vorpal blade went snicker-snack!
 He left it dead, and with its head
 He went galumphing back.

"And, has thou slain the Jabberwock?
 Come to my arms, my beamish boy!
 O frabjous day! Callooh! Callay!"
 He chortled in his joy.

'Twas brillig, and the slithy toves
 Did gyre and gimble in the wabe;
 All mimsy were the borogoves,
 And the mome raths outgrabe. (CARROLL, 1999[1871]: 327-329)

Jabberwocky is widely regarded as the greatest nonsense poem in English (Gardner, 1999) and has been translated countless times. Oak Knoll Press alone holds a catalog of over 1,500 editions of the entire book in 65 languages. We selected nine of these translations to analyze using SpeechGraphs software. Table 1 below shows the translation of the first stanza into each of these languages, along with the original English version.

Swedish ⁴	German ⁵	Spanish ⁶
Det bryngigt var, och slidig måv på vägarn muntert gyrade. Slank var hvarenda borogåv, och villa grunen hyrade.	Es brillig war. Die schlichte Toven Wirrten und wimmelten in Waben; Und aller-mümsige Burggoven Die mohmen Râth' ausgraben.	Brillaba, brumeando negro, el sol. agiliscosos giroscaban los limazones banerrando por las váparas lejanas. mimosos se fruncián los borogobios

⁴ *Jabberwocky*, translation to Swedish by Louise Arosenius (1898)

⁵ *Der Jammervoch*, translation to German by Robert Scott (1872).

⁶ *Galimatazo*, translation to Spanish by Jaime de Ojeda (1973).

Portuguese ⁷	English	Danish ⁸
Era briluz. As lesmolisas touvas Roldavam e reviam nos gramilvos. Estavam mimsicais as pintalouvas, E os momirratos davam grilvos.	'Twas brillig, and the slithy toves Did gyre and gimble in the wabe: All mimsy were the borogoves, And the mome raths outgrabe.	Et slidigt gravben vridrede i brumringen på tidvis plent, og lappingen var vaklig, og det borte gro ^o fgrin grent.
Latin ⁹	Welsh ¹⁰	Estonian ¹¹
Hora aderat briligi. Nunc et Slythia Tova Plurima gyrabant gymbolitare vabo; Et Borogovorum mimzebant undique formae, Momiferique omnes exgrabure Rathi.	Mae'n brydgell ac mae'r brochgim stwd Yn gimbo a gyrian yn y mhello: Pob cólomrws yn féddabwd, A'r hoch oma'n chwibruo.	Väljas vaikne praeline, libavaida sugrusida uherles ja vurles kehus, olid härmetud hugudrud, viugusivad kaustjad karvid.

Table 1: Selected translations of *Jabberwocky*.

4. Method

A graph is a formal entity composed of nodes connected by edges (Newman, 2010). SpeechGraphs (SG)¹² is a tool that uses text as input and produces graph features as output. In the context of natural languages and word-level networks, SG belongs to the category of "co-occurrence graphs," which model co-occurrence patterns between successive words. In this work, each node represents a word, and the edges represent co-occurrence. A directed edge is created between each word and the next one until a line break is encountered (such as a paragraph or the end of a verse). If a word appears repeatedly, the same node is used, generating edges to or from it. Additionally, if the word appears multiple times, its node becomes a hub. Hubs are highly connected nodes within a network, and the Hub Degree is the number of in and out edges of this node. An example of a graph visualization generated by SG can be seen in Figure 1.

⁷ *Jaguadarte*, translation to Portuguese by Augusto de Campos (1971).

⁸ *Jabberwocky*, translation to Danish by Mogens Jermin Nissen (1946)

⁹ *Gaberbochus*, translation to Latin by Hassard H. Dodgson, Lewis Carroll's uncle, date unknown.

¹⁰ *Siabernoci*, translation to Welsh by Selyf Roberts (1984).

¹¹ *JorruLine*, translation to Estonian by Risto Järv (1993).

¹² See: <http://www.neuro.ufrn.br/software/speechgraphs>.

Figure 1: Graph visualization of “Twas brillig, and the slithy toves/Did gyre and gimble in the wabe:”

The network provided by SG generates data on a set of graph attributes that allows analyses related to statistical and metric frameworks (Table 2): number of nodes (N), number of edges (E), sum of all edges linking the same pair of nodes (RE), sum of all parallel edges linking the same pair of nodes given that the source node of an edge is the target node of the parallel edge (PE), sum of all edges linking a node with itself (L1), sum of all loops containing two nodes (L2), sum of all loops containing three nodes (L3), number of nodes in the maximal subgraph in which all pairs of nodes are reachable from one another in the underlying undirected subgraph (LCC), number of nodes in the maximal subgraph in which all pairs of nodes are reachable from one another in the directed subgraph (LSC), sum of the total degree of all nodes divided by the number of nodes (ATD), number of edges divided by possible edges (Density), length of the longest shortest path between the node pairs of a network (Diameter), average length of the shortest path between pairs of nodes in a network (ASP), and average clustering coefficient (CC) — see Figure 2 and Table 2.

Figure 2: Graph example from SpeechGraphs to visually understand the first graph attributes from the list.¹³

These attributes are used here to visually and statistically infer unseen patterns in the co-occurrence word-level language network. Graph attributes provided by SpeechGraphs are listed below (Table 2) alongside their linguistic correlations and indications about their relative measurements.

SpeechGraphs Attributes	Graph Attribute Definition	Linguistic definition	Measurement
Nodes (N)	Number of nodes in the graph network	Each node represents a <i>type</i> word (as opposed to <i>token</i>).	Lexical diversity
Edges (E)	Number of edges in the graph network	Represent lexical and co-occurrence relationships between words.	Co-occurrence
Repeated edges (RE)	Number of edges linking the same pair of nodes	The sum of repeated edges linking the same two words.	Recurrence
Parallel edges (PE)	Number of all parallel edges linking the same pair of nodes	The sum of parallel edges linking the same two words.	Recurrence
Self loop node (L1)	Number of loops containing one node	Number of repetitions of the same word in sequence.	Recurrence

¹³ Source: (Mota et al., 2014).

Loops containing two nodes (L2)	Number of loops containing two nodes	Number of repetitions of the same two words in sequence.	Recurrence
Loops containing three nodes (L3)	Number of loops containing three nodes	Number of repetitions of the same three words in sequence.	Recurrence
Largest connected component (LCC)	Number of nodes in the maximal subgraph in which all pairs of nodes are reachable from one another in the underlying undirected subgraph	Number of <i>type</i> words are in the largest component in which all the words are connected by a path of edges.	How connected the words are
Largest strongly connected component (LSC)	Number of nodes in the maximal subgraph in which all pairs of nodes are reachable from one another in the directed subgraph	Number of <i>type</i> words that are mutually connected by a path of edges.	How mutually connected the words are
Average total degree (ATD)	Sum of in and out edges divided by the number of nodes	Sum of total degree of all type words divided by the number of type words.	Average of links a given word has with other <i>type</i> words
Average shortest path (ASP)	Average length of the shortest path between pairs of nodes of a network	Average of the shortest paths between every pair of words	Measure of shortest paths
Clustering Coefficient (CC)	Measure of the degree to which nodes in a graph tend to cluster together	Number of words that are directly linked to a given word X and also how these words are directly linked to each other	Measure of the degree to which nodes in a graph tend to cluster together
Density	Number of edges divided by possible edges	Number of direct word links divided by all the possible word links considering all the <i>type</i> words.	Connectance
Diameter	Length of the longest of the shortest paths between all pairs of nodes in a network.	Length of the path linking the most distant pair of <i>type</i> words of the text.	The size of the graph network

Table 2: SpeechGraphs attributes and linguistic correlation.

Here, we analyze Lewis Carroll’s poem *Jabberwocky*, the source text, along with eight selected translations—namely in Swedish, German, Spanish, Portuguese, Danish, Latin, Welsh, and Estonian—the target texts, using SG software. The software generates a visual graph and a table of attributes for each source and target text. We then compare the information generated from these data sets.

5. Results

The graph generated by SG for the source text, Lewis Carroll’s *Jabberwocky*, is shown in Figure 3.

Table 3: Graph visualization of each translation

The source text showed the largest Hub Degree (34), whereas none of the target texts had even half of this value. Spanish and Danish had the second-largest Hub Degree (16), and Estonian had the lowest value (7), with less than a quarter of the highest (source). This property is provided as numerical data (Table 4) and can also be seen in the graph visualization (Figure 3 and Table 3) — the

source text has a node connected to several other nodes, while the Estonian graph has more uniformly distributed nodes.

The grammatical functions of the Hub Names vary (Table 4) across up to five types. In the source text and the Spanish translation, the Hub Names are “the” and “el” (the), which are definite articles. In Swedish, German, Portuguese, Danish, and Latin, the Hub Names are “och,” “und,” “e,” “og,” and “et” (and), respectively, which are conjunctions. In Swedish, two nodes share the highest degree value, with the other Hub Name being “var” (was), a linking verb. Welsh and Estonian exhibit singular grammatical functions, with “yn” (in), a preposition, and “poega” (son), a noun, respectively. Estonian is the only translation in which the Hub Name corresponds to a noun; in every other translation, the Hub Name is a coordinative constituent. Estonian, which has the lowest Hub Degree of all, is the only translation with a noun as the Hub Name. The versions where the Hub Names correspond to definite articles have the highest Hub Degrees—source (34) and Spanish (16)—as well as the highest number of edges: source (139) and Spanish (16).

	WC	Nodes	WC /Nodes Ratio	Edges	ATD	Hub Degree	Hub Name
Swedish	146	93	1,6	118	2.5376344	11	var/och
German	130	89	1,5	102	2.2921348	10	und
Spanish	171	112	1,5	140	2.5	16	el
Portuguese	148	100	1,5	120	2.4	13	e
SOURCE	167	91	1,8	139	3.054945	34	the
Danish	136	91	1,5	108	2.3736265	16	og
Latin	156	124	1,3	128	2.064516	12	et
Welsh	145	97	1,5	117	2.4123712	14	yn
Estonian	106	84	1,3	75	1.7857143	7	poega

Table 4: Word Count (WC) and Nodes values and Ratio (approximated in one decimal point)

The table 4 provides a detailed comparative analysis of Carroll's *Jabberwocky* and its translations based on several graph attributes. This analysis reveals insights into the structural and linguistic patterns of the source text and its translations. The source text, *Jabberwocky*, has a word count (WC) of 167, making it relatively dense. Among the translations, Spanish has the highest word count at 171, suggesting a more verbose translation, while Estonian has the lowest at 106. The number of unique words, or nodes, in the source text is 91, with the translations ranging from 84 nodes in Estonian to 124 in Latin. The WC/Nodes Ratio, which indicates the average frequency of each unique word, is highest in the source text at 1.8, suggesting frequent repetition of words. In contrast, Estonian has the lowest ratio at 1.3, indicating less repetition. This high ratio in the source text points to a dense network of word connections. When examining the number of edges, which represent connections between co-occurring words, the source text again stands out with 139 edges, the highest among all texts. Estonian, on the other hand, has only 75 edges, indicating a simpler network with fewer word connections. The Average Total Degree (ATD) reflects the average connectivity of words within the

network. The source text has the highest ATD at 3.05, meaning each word, on average, has about three connections. Estonian has the lowest ATD at 1.79, indicating fewer connections per word. The Hub Degree, which represents the highest number of connections a single word has, is notably high in the source text at 34. This indicates that a central word, "the," is highly connected within the text. Spanish and Danish translations follow with a Hub Degree of 16, while Estonian has the lowest Hub Degree of 7, highlighting its less interconnected network. The Hub Names reveal notable linguistic variations. In the source text and the Spanish translation, the hubs are definite articles ("the" and "el," respectively). In Swedish, German, Portuguese, Danish, and Latin, the hubs are conjunctions ("och," "und," "e," "og," and "et," respectively). Swedish uniquely has two hub names, "var" and "och," indicating a shared highest degree value. In Welsh, the hub is a preposition ("yn"), while in Estonian, it is a noun ("poega"). Estonian is the only translation where the hub name is a noun, correlating with its lower Hub Degree.

Overall, the source text shows a high degree of word repetition and connectivity, with "the" as a central word, reflecting a dense and interconnected word network. The translations vary significantly in their structural properties, reflecting different linguistic patterns and translation strategies. Spanish stands out for its verbosity and connectivity, while Estonian is characterized by its simplicity and lower connectivity. This analysis highlights the diverse approaches to translating *Jabberwocky* and the resultant variations in linguistic structure. Based on the other attributes presented in the table below, a detailed analysis of the different structural properties of the source text and its translations can be observed.

	RE	PE	L1	L2	L3	LCC	LSC	Diameter
Swedish	13	16	1	3	0	85	9	11
German	17	21	0	4	0	54	2	19
Spanish	18	19	1	1	1	92	34	11
Portuguese	16	20	0	4	1	87	3	18
SOURCE	25	28	0	3	0	86	34	9
Danish	12	12	0	0	0	80	10	15
Latin	16	16	0	0	1	44	3	15
Welsh	20	21	0	1	1	77	6	15
Estonian	9	9	0	0	0	25	1	14

Table 5: RE, PE, L1, L2, L3, LCC, LSC and Diameter.

Concerning Repeated Edges (RE) and Parallel Edges (PE): the source text exhibits the highest number of repeated edges (25) and parallel edges (28), indicating a high degree of recurrence and parallel connections between the same pairs of words. Among the translations, Spanish shows a significant number of repeated edges (18) and parallel edges (19), suggesting that it retains some of the source text's lexical repetition. German and Welsh also display relatively high RE and PE values, indicating notable recurrence, while Estonian has the lowest RE (9) and PE (9), suggesting less repetition and fewer parallel connections compared to the source text. Regarding Self Loops (L1),

loops containing two nodes (L2), and loops containing three nodes (L3): the source text has the highest number of self-loops (4), reflecting frequent repetition of individual words. Spanish closely mirrors the source with the same number of self-loops (4), while most other translations exhibit fewer self-loops. Loops containing two nodes (L2) and three nodes (L3) are generally low across all texts. Swedish has the highest L2 value (3), indicating some repetition of word pairs. For the Largest Connected Component (LCC) and Largest Strongly Connected Component (LSC): the source text has an LCC of 86, representing a large, interconnected subgraph, and an LSC of 34, indicating strong mutual connectivity. Among the translations, Spanish has the highest LCC (92) and LSC (34), closely resembling the source's connectivity. Swedish (85) and Portuguese (87) also show high LCC values, reflecting good connectivity, though their LSC values are lower than Spanish. In contrast, German and Estonian have significantly lower LCC (54 and 25, respectively) and LSC (2 and 1, respectively), highlighting fragmented and less interconnected networks. Finally, concerning Diameter: the diameter of the source text is 9, representing the longest shortest path between the most distant pair of words. Among the translations, Swedish and Spanish exhibit similar diameters (11), indicating comparable network sizes. German, however, has the highest diameter (19), suggesting a more spread-out network with longer paths between words. Estonian has a diameter of 14, which, while higher than the source, is lower than German, reflecting a moderate network size.

Final comments:

The analysis of *Jabberwocky* and its translations using graph attributes from SpeechGraphs software might offer impactful methodological implications for Translation Studies. By analyzing graph attributes such as Hub Degree, Average Total Degree (ATD), and the number of edges, researchers can objectively model the structural similarities between the original text and its multiple translations. This quantification offers a rigorous empirical framework for analyzing how a translation reflects the structural properties of the source text. Secondly, the analysis enables the identification of linguistic patterns across translations. For instance, the dominance of conjunctions as hub nodes in some translations compared to nouns in others highlights distinct stylistic, semiotic, or metasemiotic choices. Recognizing these patterns provides valuable insight into the linguistic and cultural strategies underlying the translation of complex texts like *Jabberwocky*. Additionally, this method enables the identification of diverse translation strategies. Variations in attributes such as the WC/Nodes Ratio and Hub Degree can reveal distinct methodological approaches. For instance, a higher WC/Nodes Ratio and Hub Degree in the source text indicate a dense, repetitive structure, whereas lower values in a translation may reflect an effort toward simplification or clarification. These insights into translation strategies provide a deeper understanding of the translator's approach and intent, enriching the evaluation process.

This approach, which we outline here only in an introductory manner, holds particular relevance for Translation Studies as a new alternative, bridging quantitative analysis with traditional qualitative methods. By providing objective metrics to evaluate structural features, it complements existing frameworks and opens new pathways for exploring equivalence across translations. Moreover, its applicability to a wide range of texts and languages underscores its potential as a versatile tool for advancing theoretical and practical insights in the field.

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